

UNDERSTANDING EXPERIENCES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE MODULAR LEARNING DELIVERY IMPLEMENTATION

¹Ulysses R. Pamatian, ²Edwin Espinosa, EdD, ³Emie A. Genton, PhD

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

Graduate School

General Santos City, Philippines

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Abstract: The purpose of this phenomenological study is to describe the experiences of senior high school teachers of South Glan District, Division of Sarangani who have been implementing modular learning delivery and to look into their different perspectives. Qualitative design wearing phenomenological approach determined how these teachers made meaning of the modular learning delivery at their specific school by making analysis of the participant's view, feeling and impacts to their lives and workplace. There were 5 participants who underwent in the in-depth interview. The generated themes revealed that senior high school teachers viewed modular learning delivery as difficulties and challenges, assessment problems, challenges and flexibility, lack of resources and distribution and retrieval problems. Regarding their feelings about the modular learning delivery, the participants conveyed that they feel the fear, exhausted, worries and burn-out. Furthermore, for the impacts of the modular learning delivery to the lives of the participants and workplace, they become sensitive and time and work oriented. The data were also compared, weighed, and linked to recent researches about modular learning delivery implementation.

Keywords: Modular learning delivery, views, feelings, impact, experiences, senior high, school students, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted education and teacher education in particular various ways. School Year 2020 - 2021 is described as the beginning of "Education in the New Normal. The sudden transition from face-to-face learning to distance learning threatened not only the parents and students, but most significantly, the Department of Education. It aims despite the changes in the delivery of knowledge, the worth of the education stays the same.

As the country continues to encounter different issues brought about by the COVID19 pandemic, the Department of Education addresses the challenges in primary education over its Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) under the Department of Education Order No. 012, s. 2020 which aims to safeguard the health, safety, and well-being of the learners, teachers, and personnel during COVID-19 while finding ways for education to continue amidst the crisis. It must be learned throughout life. It is an essential educational skill, especially about academic achievement and life-long learning (Eddy, Herman, and Reinke, 2019; Usher and Schunk, 2018; Nardo, 2017).

In particular, the BE-LCP has been designed with a legal framework responsive to the "new normal," keeping in mind the constitutional mandate to uphold the right of all citizens to quality education at all times. The Department of Education ensures that all learners have access to quality Basic Education. They distributed Self Learning Modules (SLMs) used by the learners and chose the modalities suited for them.

As a consequence of these shutdowns, teachers were confronted with abrupt changes, both in their teaching and learning and in their daily lives as a whole. Distance learning demands a large amount of self-regulation, particularly putting the students at risk of missing out on broader learning opportunities and being overwhelmed by the requirements to acquire and understand academic content with reduced or minimal support from their teachers. Moreover, the lack of physical manifestation and the lesser extent of informal discussion and spontaneous interaction with classmates, friends, and teachers increase the risk of developing negative emotions and feelings of loneliness (Pelikan, Lüftenegger, Holzer, Korlat, Spiel, and Schober, 2021; Padmapriya, 2016; Sadeghi, 2019).

As a result, teachers and students have to adapt to remote teaching rapidly. Teacher education is no exemption. The need to create learning environments for the students and teachers doing their preparation implied decisions, choices, and adaptations to meet the expectations of the students and the requirements of teacher education, and the conditions in which both universities and schools need to follow. The rapid, unexpected, and 'forced' transition from face-to-face to remote teaching has entailed several challenges and constraints. Despite the limited information about the virus, the necessity to make quick decisions prompted the higher education to transition to remote learning rapidly. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, modern-day crises in higher education were limited in both time and geographic location (Flores & Gago, 2020; American College Health Association, 2020; Friestad-Tate, Schubert & McCoy, 2016).

As far as teacher teaching is concerned, the institutions and stakeholders adapted to the new scenario created by the COVID-19 pandemic as well as the training strategies and experiences of innovation (Bao 2020; Flores and Gago 2020; Quezada, Talbot, and Quezada-Parker 2020; Zhang, Wang, Yang, & Wang 2020; Ferdig, Baumgartner, Hartshorne, Kaplan-Rakowski, Mouza & Eds. 2020). The worth of teacher-student interaction and a teacher's competence in applying appropriate distance learning pedagogy and providing timely and informative feedback turned out to be predictive for the differences in learning success and learning investment of students during the school shutdown (Huber and Helm, 2020; Holmes, Nguyen, Zhang, Reintes, 2019; Tuscano, 2020).

While the accounts of how higher education organizations and teacher educators responded to the transition from face-to-face to modular teaching are relevant, more needs are to be done in this regard. For informed and productive modular education and learning, it is essential to know more about its potential and use. As such, it is necessary to go beyond emergency modular learning delivery practices and develop quality modular teaching and learning that result from careful instructional design and planning (Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust, & Bond, 2020; Lowell & Champion, 2020; Lindug, 2021).

Furthermore, the school closure affected the low- and high-achieving students, demonstrating that while self-regulated learning is feasible for high achieving and high-motivated students, it is challenging especially for students with low academic achievement and learning motivation (Grewenig, Lergetporer, Werner, Woessmann, and Zierow, 2020; Kanchan, 2016; Marin, Taylor, Shapiro, & Hall, 2020).

Lastly, focusing on how the current situation has forced several school teacher education programs to adapt to a modular format may provide a broad understanding of adopted ways. Yet, it is necessary to make sure that these ways are effective. Therefore, this is a crucial moment to synthesize the effort that has been done to inform future practices. This period of change requires the necessity to provide an evidence-based perception on what works and does not work, but most importantly, to know the characteristics, the processes, the outcomes, the implications, and the experiences of teachers in implementing modular learning delivery practices.

Statement of the Problem

Recently, the world has encountered a global pandemic, and one of the many affected institutions is the Department of Education. To ensure that learning and classes remain unhampered, the DepEd continues planning, implementing, and evaluating programs to address issues relevant to education amidst the crisis brought by COVID-19. Currently, the department is implementing many learning delivery modalities for learning continuity among the learners, and the most common is the modular learning delivery modality. This modality is a big challenge for both the teachers and the learners as it appears something new to them. This calls for an 'adopt quickly' reaction to the new normal in teaching and learning amidst the pandemic (Tumapon, 2020; Lim, 2016; Viner, Russel, Croker, Packer, Ward, Stansfield, & Booy, 2020).

This provides additional risks on the teachers' part, especially during the distribution and retrieval of printed modules. Furthermore, this study seeks to find out pertinent issues about the experiences of senior high school teachers as to their views and impact of the implementation of modular learning delivery in the south Glan District Division of Sarangani.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to learn about the experiences of senior high school teachers in the South Glan District in implementing modular learning delivery in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. As well as the trials they faced when switching from face-to-face classes to distance modular learning delivery implementation in education. The participants shared their stories from their respective experiences as senior high school teachers who carry out the teaching and learning process among the learners in different educational settings concerning this new standard scenario (Zhao, Guo, Xiao, Zhu, Sun, Huang, 2020; Robosa, 2021; Viner, Russel, Croker, Packer, Ward, Stansfield, & Booy, 2020).

Furthermore, another purpose of this phenomenological study is to fully understand the significant meanings of such experiences. Moreover, it was expected that this phenomenological study research would help me understand and extend an in-depth appreciation of the experiences among public senior high school teachers. In the same way, as this will be read by many, this would turn them to examine their own extraordinary and meaningful experiences relevant to the participants' experiences and empower them to better understand their walks of life through the help of this research endeavor.

Research Questions

This study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do the experiences of Senior High School teachers in the modular learning delivery implementation be described?
 - 1.1 How do they view their experiences in the implementation of modular learning delivery?
 - 1.2 How do they feel about the modular learning delivery implementation?
 - 1.3 How does the implementation of modular learning delivery affect the lives of the participants?

Theoretical Lens

The theory underpinning this research was the Transactional Distance advanced, since this study involves distance learning specifically modular distance learning modality. This theory states the idea that distance education is not simply a geographic separation of learners and teachers, but more importantly, is a pedagogical concept. It is pointed out that when talking about distance education, it is typically talking about a teaching environment where the separation between the teacher and learner is significant enough, that special teaching-learning strategies and techniques must be used. It is a concept describing the aspect of teacher-learner relationships that exist when the learners and instructors are separated by space or by time (Moore, 2016; Culatta, 2020; Basilan, 2018).

Due to the unique environment of distance learning, teachers and learners experienced more of a distance due to the physical distance that separated these two groups. Although separation by space and time are the most prominent characteristics of distance education, transactional distance is the actual guiding principle in distance education, influencing the process of teaching and learning (Weidlich & Bastiaen, 2018; Delgaty, 2018; Casteel, 2020).

This theory is relevant to the study as this provided framework on the principle of distance learning. The distance learning theory is widely used in distance education both online environment and modular pedagogy. The assumption of this theory was used in this study, since it assesses the views, feelings and impacts of modular distance learning modality in which the teacher and the learners are unconnected both physical and synchronicity of time.

Delimitations and Limitations of the study

This interpretative phenomenological study results cannot be generalized ideas. Thus, this study is limited to teachers based on the given questions by the researcher and other available documents of five (5) public senior high school teachers of South Glan District who were the participants of the study. This study is primarily designed to have an in-depth understanding and analysis of different teachers' experiences concerning their views, feelings, impacts as they implement modular learning delivery in their respective schools.

Moreover, the nature of the study used a simple interrogation between the researcher and the respondents using recording materials such as a cellular phone or tape recorder so the respondents' responses may be replayed by the researcher in case there is a doubt about the answers of the respondents (Creswell, 2018; Vogt and Johnson, 2019; Alemu, 2020).

Participants and non-participants observation, in-depth interviews, semi-structured interviews, unstructured interviews, dialogic interviewing were conducted using a qualitative phenomenological technique (Madison 2018; Smith and Larkin, 2019; Alemu, 2020; Vogt and Johnson, 2019). Finally, this study was narrowed by the findings not intended for generalization to other research settings.

2. PROCEDURES

The Rationale for the Qualitative Methodology and Design

Qualitative research is a method for discovering and understanding the meaning of individual's lives or groups ascribed to a social or human problem. Furthermore, a phenomenological approach was chosen to allow the researcher to understand better the participants' views, feelings, and impact on their lives. Phenomenology focuses on documenting how the subjects experience a particular phenomenon and it is a prevalent method of inquiry (Creswell, & Poth, 2018; Vogt and Johnson, 2019; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

For this study, the researcher conducted face-to-face interviews with the identified senior high school teachers of South Glan District, Glan Sarangani Province. The researcher utilized interviews to fully understand the experiences of the participants from their perspectives, and as a qualitative (phenomenology) researcher, it is the role and responsibility of the researcher to examine and interpret the impact of the research subject matter on the lived experiences of the research participants towards modular learning delivery implementation (Alemu, 2020; Creswell, & Poth, 2018; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

The exploration of this phenomenon frequently takes place in the participant's setting. It is carried out using data collection tools that allow for immersion into the participants' experiences. Furthermore, it is a qualitative research method that endeavors to explore and to understand the dominant discourses seen as being the right way to think, see, talk about or enact a particular action or situation in the society and recommend ways to re-dress social power inequities (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Parkenson & Drislane 2015; Smith and Larkin, 2019)

By developing a feeling of interpreting, a given experience, qualitative research analyzes concepts in their natural context. Moreover, phenomenology focuses on understanding social-cultural and psychological occurrences from the people involved (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Creswell & Poth, 2018; Bowen, 2019). Phenomenology maintains the efforts to understand human behavior that human beings are rational beings who perceive and make sense of the world and the world around them (Smith and Larkin, 2019; Crossman, 2017; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Finally, an interpretative phenomenology approach was used. Interpretative Phenomenology allows multiple individuals (participants) who experience similar events to tell their stories without distortions and prosecutions. Creswell (2018) stated that "a phenomenological study describes the common meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or phenomenon." He also said that "Phenomenologists focus on describing what all participants have in common as they experience a phenomenon." The researcher's insights and interpretations become part of the research, and as a result, a subjective and interpretative orientation flows throughout the process of inquiry (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Smith and Larkin, 2019).

Site and Samples

In this study, purposeful sampling was utilized. Purposeful sampling is a qualitative procedure in which the researcher intentionally selects individuals and sites to learn or understand a specific issue. It is suggested that "when selecting the participants for a study, it is important to determine the size of the sample you will need." Furthermore, he also stated that in any qualitative research study, it is essential that "you select people or site that can best help you understand the central phenomenon" (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Smith and Larkin, 2019; Crossman, 2017).

In addition, the participants of this study were selected according to the following inclusion criteria: **a)** permanent public senior high school teachers of South Glan District in the Division of Sarangani **b)** they have been teaching in their respective schools for three years and above and **c)** they should be regular teachers in Department of Education, Division of Sarangani especially in South

Glan District.

Participant 1 is a 28-year-old female teacher from Valeria B. Lopez Integrated School. She graduated with a degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Social Studies and has been teaching for almost five (5) years in her teaching career.

Participant 2 is a 39-year-old female teacher currently teaching in Leonard Young Sr. National High School. She graduated Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English and taught for almost four (4) years. She is also a bonafide resident of Big Margus, where she is currently teaching.

Participant 3 is a 29-year-old female teacher, also currently teaching in Leonard Young Sr. National High School. She graduated Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English and has been a public senior high school teacher for almost four (4) years. She is also a bonafide resident of the barangay where she is currently teaching. Participant 4 is a 32-year-old male teacher, also currently teaching in Pangyan National High School. He graduated Bachelor of Secondary Education major in science and has been a public senior high school teacher for almost four (4) years. He is a resident of General Santos City, but presently teaching in Pangyan Glan Sarangani, where the school is located.

Participant 5 is a 35-year-old male teacher, also currently teaching in Pangyan National High School. He graduated Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics and has been a public senior high school teacher for almost four (5) years. A teacher with passion and a resident of Barangay Pangyan Glan, Sarangani.

Access and Permission

The following processes were observed during the data collection to acquire access and asked permission to perform the research. Through the school principal of Valeria B. Lopez Integrated School, Leonard Young Sr. National High School, and Pangyan National High School, the researcher requested access to the research location and consent for the conduct of the study. The researcher gave the individuals an informed consent letter after it was approved. As a result, the researcher advised the participants to decline their invitation if they felt uncomfortable in doing so. After the participants agreed, the timetable was created based on their availability of time.

Furthermore, the participants were oriented to the interview procedure and discussion and were made aware of the confidentiality of their responses. The researcher informed the participants that he would videotape the in-depth interview. It was audio-recorded, and the researcher transcribed everything. He also gave a consent certificate to the participants and asked them to sign as proof that an in-depth interview had occurred.

Data Gathering Strategies

The interpretative design was used for the research. These are the studies in which participants' viewpoints or concerns and abilities of a subject are determined. The researcher prepared and designed the semi-structured questionnaire with the guidance of his adviser before gathering the data. Semi-structured questions aimed to discover the participants' descriptions of their experiences in implementing modular learning delivery. Upon the approval of the conduct of the study, the researcher also used a focused group discussion for encoding the data (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2016; Creswell & Poth, 2018; Billups, 2020).

The researcher also prepared the venue, equipment/materials, such as an audio recorder, video camera, writing materials, and a copy of the interview guide needed for the interview. The researcher made sure that the place was conducive and that every participant was comfortable and free to refuse to participate if they changed their mind. Then, the researcher discussed and handled the participant's interview protocol forms, which contained background questions and the house rules for the interview sessions.

Furthermore, the researcher interviewed the participants in their respective classroom during their free time. Each participant was set on different dates and times. All information was audio and video recorded with the permission of the participants. The researcher extended gratitude and thanks to each participant every end of the session.

After each interview, the participants listened to the recorded data to check the accuracy and clarity of their shared recorded information. The researcher kept all the audio-recorded data to register what had transpired during the interview; gestures were also integrated into the transcribed narrative text (Mills, Durepos, & Wiebe, 2018; Vogt and Johnson, 2019; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

The researcher then transcribed the audio-video recordings of the information shared by the participants for checking. After checking, they affix their signature to ensure the reliability of the data gathered, strict record-keeping manifesting a good decision trait, and providing interpretations of the data are consistent and transparent. After the transcription, the researcher emerged the data for analysis (Noble, 2015; Smith, Flowers, Larken, 2019; Fejszes, 2017).

Data Analysis Procedures

As pointed out, the data analysis in a research study involves summarizing the mass of data collected and presenting the results to communicate the essential features. In every data collected, the analysis followed. This is when the researcher tried to break down all the information gathered to understand them better so that every component will be placed in its particular order to give due description and meaning to it (Hancock, Amankwaa, Revell, & Mueller, 2019; Bowen, 2019; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

The data analysis approach was also based on Creswell's & Creswell (2018) procedures in analyzing and interpreting the data. These include reading through the data to develop an overall understanding of it, describing it in detail, establishing a context. Reporting of the findings will be based primarily on the description of the phenomenon on the experiences of senior high school teachers in modular learning delivery implementation.

Researcher's Role and Potential Ethical Issues

I took this kind of research to capture the critical phenomenon of the senior high school teachers' experiences in implementing modular learning delivery. Since this study has a special meaning to me, and I wanted to access the thoughts and feelings of the participants of the study, this is not an easy undertaking. It involves asking the individuals to talk about the things that may be very personal to them. At times, the experiences being explored were fresh in the participant's mind, whereas in other instances, reliving past experiences may be difficult.

After identifying the possible participants of my chosen study, I immediately gave them a letter of invitation and a consent form. My study focused on the five (5) participants. I became a facilitator of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). As a facilitator, I prepared an interview guide as a frame of reference or topic points during the focus group discussion. During the FGD, the participants shared their views, opinions, feelings, and impacts of modular learning delivery. The interviewer often undertakes FGD with a small group of people with a common interest (Creswell, & Poth, 2018; Morgan, 2018; Fejszes, 2017).

After the data were collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard the participants and their data. Before the research begins, mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to the participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board. As a researcher, I am fully aware that I have to examine and meet the professional association standards and seek approval from the institution and the participants involved in the study before conducting the research. I need to select a site with no vested interest and negotiate authorship for publication (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Swinton and Mowat, 2019; Bowen, 2019).

According to the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), "good research should be well adjusted, well-planned, appropriately designed, and ethically approved. To research, a lower standard may constitute misconduct." This may appear to be a stringent criterion, but it highlights the essential requirement of a researcher to conduct the research responsibly. To achieve this, a research protocol should be developed and adhered to. It must be carefully agreed by all the contributors and collaborators, including matters of authorship and publications.

The ethical considerations in conducting a research are not a reflection or side note to the research study. It is an essential aspect of research that needs to remain at the forefront of our work.

First is the Validity. The research design must focus on specific research questions. Hence, the decisions of the study must correlate to the questions posed and the results. Also, research ethics stresses that the methods used must relate specifically to the research questions.

Second, Voluntary Participation and Consent, an individual should at no point feel any pressure to participate in a study. This includes any type of belief or deception in trying to gain an individual's trust. Informed consent says that an individual must give explicit consent to participate in the study by providing a consent form as an agreement of trust between the researcher and the participants.

Third, you need to explain why you want to study a particular group of participants. In addition, if your sample includes kids or with individuals of special needs you will have additional requirements to address, like parental permission.

Fourth, confidentiality, the third ethics principle of the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), states that: "The confidentiality of the information presented by research subjects and the anonymity of respondents must be respected." However, sometimes confidentiality is limited. For example, if a participant is at risk of harm, we must protect him/her.

Fifth, Risk of Harm we should do everything in our power to protect the participants of the study. For this, we should focus on the risk-to-benefit ratio. If possible, risks outweigh the benefits, and then we should abandon or redesign the study. The risk of harm also requires us to measure the risk-to-benefit ratio as the investigation progresses.

Lastly, plagiarism ranges from unreferenced use of other's published and unpublished ideas, including research grant applications, to submission under "new" authorship of a complete paper, sometimes in a different language. Therefore, it is necessary to disclose all sources of information, and if a large amount of other people's written or illustrative materials was used, permission must be sought.

In conclusion, it is the researcher's duty to ensure that the research is conducted ethically and responsibly from planning to publication. Researchers and authors should familiarize themselves with these principles and follow them strictly. If in doubt, it is advisable to consult knowledgeable people for their expert opinions.

Methods of Validation

The participants of the study were all regular public senior high school teachers of the South Glan District. They were limited to only five participants, and three of them were female and two males. The researcher identified these teachers as implementers of modular learning delivery of South Glan District Division of Sarangani. Moreover, these participants were eager to share their experiences, feelings, and impacts on the study.

To boost the validity of the findings, the researcher did member checking as it focused on the validity procedures directly done with the participants in the research study. It is the most critical procedure for establishing credibility in the study; it involves gathering of data and analyzing them back to the participants of the research study for them to confirm the reliability of the information as well as the narrative description transcribed from the notes taken by the researcher (Lincoln and Guba, 2018; Wolcott, 2017; Rubin, & Rubin, 2019).

The researcher transcribed the audio recordings after the interview process and utilized member checking as a validation method. The participants examined and confirmed the contents of the interview transcripts and affixed their signatures on them. Such a validation process signaled the trustworthiness of the data.

Moreover, the concept of a member checking enhances validity. During the member checking, the researcher showed the raw data for the participants to study and asked them if the themes or categories made sense and developed with enough proof and whether the overall account was realistic and accurate. When the analysis was complete, and the final model was established, the researcher invited each participant to show the findings to check and give their feedback. Examining the participants' results can be a valuable part of the analysis and enhance validity (Swinton & Mowat, 2019; Rubin, 2020; Creswell, & Poth, 2018).

3. DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results, comparison of finding with existing studies, limitations of the research, implication for the future research study, and the overall significance of the qualitative research on the experiences of senior high school teachers in modular learning delivery in South Glan District Division of Sarangani.

This study sought to support the senior high school teachers to resolve the issues and concerns related to this study, which might greatly help those who need it. This also describes the experiences of modular learning delivery implementation, especially regarding their views, feelings, and impacts on their lives and workplace. The result of the study may help the school administrators and teachers understand the plight of teaching under modular distance learning. The findings will be the bases for the necessary intervention program to help them have appropriate strategies and motivate them to have improved teaching outcomes even using non-face-to-face modality.

Major Findings

This qualitative research describes the experiences of senior high school teachers towards the implementation of modular learning delivery of the South Glan District Division of Sarangani. The following topics are the descriptions of the old high school teacher about their experiences and views of the implementation of modular learning delivery, feelings in the performance of modular learning delivery, and how this modular learning delivery implementation affects their lives as a teacher. Indeed, like many other aspects of everyday life, COVID-19 has a severe impact on students, teachers, and educational organizations around the globe (Mailizar, Almanthari, Maulina, and Bruce, 2020; Ravens-Sieberer, Kaman, Erhart, Devine, Schlack, and Otto, 2021; Sönmez, Göçmez, Uygün & Ataizi, 2018).

At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Departments of Education, both public and private institutions, rapidly moved to remote teaching or remote learning to minimize the loss of education. Remote knowledge was considered a quick alternative to face-to-face learning in time of crisis. With remote learning, under stressful circumstances, and limited time, teachers and curriculum planners have to improvise to find the best way to deliver the course content (Manfuso, 2020, Tumapon, 2020; Lim, 2016; Viner et. Al, 2020).

They did not have the advantage of careful planning and design and rigorous faculty training for modular and online courses. Instead, coursework was conducted online with collaboration tools that were available at that time. Remote teaching can be likened to telecommunicating, where the work is typically done in an office in real-time. It is conducted online using collaboration tools (Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust, & Bond. 2020; Manfuso, 2020; Masters, Taylor-Guy, Fraillon & Chase, 2020).

Additionally, the delivery of course content during remote learning is temporary. When the crisis is over, material distribution returns to its original form, such as face-to-face education—citing the differences between the rapid transition to remote teaching, where the faculty quickly move their course content to modular or online with little time to prepare. Six to nine months of design, preparation, and training are required for the rapid transition to modular delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic. It formally proposed "emergency remote teaching" as the terminology used during the COVID-19 pandemic (Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust, & Bond. 2020; Manfuso, 2020; Masters, Taylor-Guy, Fraillon & Chase, 2020).

Moving to the modular mode of teaching on an untested and unprecedented scale brings many challenges and dilemmas. This is because moving the school systems to a remote learning environment is not just a technical issue. It is a pedagogical and instructional challenge. Thus, the findings revealed that modular learning delivery as experienced by the participants gave them different challenges and difficulties. The emergency transition from face to face to the printed module and blended learning in light of COVID- 19 brings its share of challenges and complications.

In contrast to the experiences that are well planned from the beginning and designed to have printed modules, emergency remote teaching (ERT) is a temporary shift of instructional delivery to an alternate delivery model due to crisis circumstances. It involves using remote teaching solutions for instruction or education that would otherwise be delivered face-to-face or as a blended mode. It would return to that format once the crisis or emergency is abated (Hodges et al., 2020; Quinones, 2020; Mean-Chin 2020).

New protocols for distance learning on modular, require teachers to rapidly change their practices, including their daily tasks, responsibilities, and accountabilities. Teachers may be asked to develop different and varied methods to monitor children's learning (from evaluating to remediating learning losses) during the COVID crisis, including formative and summative approaches. Upon returning to school, teachers may also work hard to assess students' learning levels to see whether the learners are on track on there are any learning gaps or losses resulting from the school closure and remedial actions. Such assessments may be critical in informing the learning process and students' promotion, certification, and access to higher levels of education.

In the current context, the rapid movement to remote schooling is crucial to recognize the immense stress faced by the teachers. The stress complexes are already exhausted in the profession as the uncertainty of expectations grows. As teachers who experience unmotivated and anxiety, their wellbeing matters. They will be less effective in supporting student's well-being and student's outcomes (Ferdig, Baumgartner, Hartshorne, Kaplan-Rakowski, & Mouza, Eds. 2020; Azevedo, Hasan, Goldemberg, Iqbal, Geven, 2020; Eddy, Herman, and Reinke, 2019).

Additionally, teachers have a hard time in doing their jobs and setting priorities for their work. They have to manage and rank their task accordingly to meet the deadline and submit the necessary documents. Another through-line from the interviews was teachers' experience uncertainty and burnout. They described that experience with words such as mourning, challenges, and sadness.

Implications of the Future Research

Based on the findings, the following implications for future research are offered; The results of this study will guide the teachers, including the researcher and other future researchers, for a thorough understanding of the experiences of senior high school teachers in the implementation of modular learning delivery. Further, research may investigate the same phenomenon among teachers in other districts to evaluate the similarities and differences of their experiences in implementing modular learning delivery. These will also provide empirical data for future researchers interested in studying the experiences, feelings, and impacts of implementing modular learning in teachers' lives. Lastly, these findings may serve

as a ready reference for the research enthusiasts in identifying a research approach, a tradition of inquiry, discipline, and interpretation.

Overall Significance of the Study

The results of this study will be significant to the following:

Teachers may use the findings of this study to be guided by what will be the valuable processes to be utilized relevant to their classroom contexts. The *School Administrators* may also use the result of this study to improve more about planning and developing programs and the manner of implementing such programs for the welfare of the teachers, students, and other stakeholders. Additionally, the *learners* as the primary teachers' clientele in educational settings may appreciate and somehow be guided by this for their holistic development. Lastly, the researchers may be given a chance to understand the participants' experiences. The result of this study may be used as their future research relevant to the context of this study.

Concluding Remarks

The study focused on the experiences of senior high school teachers toward the implementation of modular learning delivery based on their views, feelings, and impacts on their lives, as well as the constructs that emerged from the information gained through in-depth interviews and one-on-one dialogue. From the study results, I can say that the Department of Education should be aware of the struggles of the teachers in this new mode of delivery. It should be more responsive to the needs of their teachers, particularly those from remote areas, because this has a significant impact on the academic performance and holistic development of the 21st-century learners, and make interventions and solutions to avoid any discrepancies in module production distribution, and report submission. Moreover, it could be seen from the data that several challenges were encountered by the teachers in Modular Distance Learning. Most students cannot study independently, and they cannot easily follow the instructions in the modules. The significant number of activities in each module and lack of resources for reproduction and delivery of modules are the problems encountered in implementing Modular Distance Learning. The Department of Education should consider this dilemma, reduce the activities, and take out the unnecessary topics to attain mastery as much as possible.

The school authorities shall also implement a system of delivery and retrieval of modules to ensure that both parents and teachers are aware of what to do and keep everyone safe from the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. The cases of COVID-19 in the Philippines are still an insignificant number, so face-to-face learning is not yet possible. However, the researcher thinks that Blended Learning is also possible for places not infected by the virus. This can be utilized in some schools located in rural areas of South Glan District Division of Sarangani. Teachers must keep on with their versatility and flexibility. They must embrace the challenge of the work responsibilities inherent to being a teacher.

Furthermore, the Department of Education and the government must collaborate towards the success of the Philippine Educational System despite the COVID-19 pandemic. Every school must be supplied with support and enough funds. The Department of Education should give autonomy and liberty to teachers in every school to do their modules. However, the modules must be validated for quality assurance, and the progress should be monitored.

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